

THE PURPOSE OF EMOJIS (SYMBOLS) USED IN TEXTS

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Abstract. *The article deals with the usage of emojis (symbols) in different language units. It is revealed that emojis are meant to be the kind of means that are mainly used in social platform discourses. The emojis are mentioned to be especially used by young people. Besides, some virtual communication is said to be observed to take place, and there must be a text formed with a specific purpose. The pragmatic sides of emojis are also touched upon in the article. The article writes that some information for intercourse needs virtual communication. Signs are meant to play an important role in order to clarify the pragmatic sides of the emojis in text language.*

Key words: *media, discourse, emoji, symbol, purpose, meaning.*

For communication, including virtual communication, there must be some information. As is known virtual communication is realized through language in written and oral form. Any language units, such as sentence, text, discourse (written and oral) means that are not language units, such as *graphemes, grapheme combinations, prosodic means, such as syllables, accents, intonations, pauses*, etc. can be considered virtual information carriers. Participants in virtual communication must use one of these means in order for communication to be two-way in the communication process. It is necessary to pay attention to the meaning and content in the communication that occurs. A word is considered to be a small unit of meaning. During virtual communication, even a single word or a single sign can create an idea. For example, a dialogue needs to be paid attention to demonstrate our point of view:

A: *I love you very much. And you?*

B: . This ‘hand sign’ means ‘*I love you too.*’ The intention of the communicator is completely clear and the communication is realized.

The main goal of such information exchange is the form for which the information is transmitted. In the different types of new media discourse, the use of such symbols, emojis, and signs expressing emotions can create a complete idea. Simply by increasing the number of signs used, the meaning and content can be further enriched.

In order any virtual communication to take place, there must be a text formed with a specific purpose. “Until recently, in linguistics, an independent and separately taken sentence was accepted as the last unit of the syntactic level in terms of hierarchical relations.In our opinion, it is precisely these shortcomings existing at the syntactic level that gives a special impetus to the emergence of such a field as text linguistics [Abdullayev 2012, p.19].

It is known that three stages of syntax were identified: traditional, communicative and structural syntax. Traditional and communicative syntax include larger language elements, that is, syntactic units and text. For this reason, the sentence can be considered to be the smallest language unit and the main conveyer of thought. K. Abdullayev noted that the sentence is not the

final, but the middle unit in the syntactic system and that this middle unit can interact with other sentences through its isomorphic and homomorphic parameters, and considered this aspect to be the cornerstone of text linguistics [Abdullayev 2012, p.19].

The use of signs and signifiers, which are already defined as a new type of communication in new media discourse, along with the units of the syntactic system within various texts, is considered inevitable.

It is known that the writing system develops by expanding the modality, or style of writing. The modality of the early writing system was mainly in the form of icons. Icon forms are constructed (created) to represent a concept through similarity. For example, the ‘sun’ icon represents the sun as it is, etc. These systems also develop to expand their scope, for example, new symbols are created to represent specific elements or other social needs, etc. The first comprehensive study of sign systems was conducted by Ch. Peirce [Peirce 1998, pp. 1-8]. Before Ch. Peirce’s research, the term icon was used to indicate images of frightening figures. It should be noted that this term can still be used in this way today. Religious icons mainly show religious figures, but each figure could be found with special distinguishing details. The facial expressions in religious icons mainly reflected the expression of somberness and piety. This was because they were not considered to be true copies of their referents. Religious icons were mostly drawn in sketch or cartoon form. For example, the Altamira carvings in Spain or the Lascaux carvings in Francemay be meant to be such examples. These carvings predate the first forms of writing by about 30,000 years.

In the new media discourse, emojis are one of the most widely encountered forms of communication, alongside symbols and signs expressing emotions.

We consider it important to write that the study of emojis is considered to be one of the most relevant topics of recent times. The word ‘emoji’ is a combination of the Japanese word *emoji*, *e-*, and *moji*. In English, *e-* is used in the meanings of *picture*, and *moji* is used in the meanings of *letter*, *character*. Thus, the word *emoji* means ‘*picture-word*’ [Danesi 2017, p.2].

Each emoji used in written texts has its own meaning. The ‘Cloud’ emoji represents the drawn pictographic form of a cloud. The ‘Sun’ emoji depicts the ideographic form of the sun rising above the horizon.

The stylistic features of the modality of emojis are value, color, and perspective. Value represents the darkness or lightness of the form. It should be emphasized that value plays a key role in describing contrasts of different types. For example, in the ‘cloud’ emoji, the color is given in the color of the cloud, that is, gray-white. In the ‘Rising Sun’ emoji, the sun rises above the horizon, etc.

M. Danesi writes that emojis aim to ensure the understanding of written texts in the global world [Danesi 2017, p.3]. For example, the emoji of *a face* or *smiling faces*. The facial expressions depicted in the emoji system were created relatively neutrally. For example, the facial colors depicted in emojis are shown in yellow. The use of yellow was used to avoid identifying racial or ethnic differences, that is, to eliminate similar facial features. The roundness of the facial shapes reflected in emojis aims to reduce the specific details of the facial structure. True, observations show that new emojis can also be created to reflect explicit cultural meanings. The emojis of *nerd* “*stupid*” and *sleuth* “*dawn*” require specific cultural ways of expression to understand the words *nerd* and *sleuth*. It can be determined that some emojis are meant to be active, while others are passive, depending on the frequency of use.

It is noteworthy to underline that each emoji has its own pragmatic meaning. Pragmatics studies the relationship between the subject who adopts and applies any sign system and that sign system. Under the term ‘pragmatic aspect’ of the texts in which emojis are used, the effect of all the elements that form it, language tools, and the set of speech methods on the addressee (recipient) is perceived. It is about giving information to the addressee, as well as influencing him/her. The speech effect in this case does not act as a component of communication, but is combined with it, and ultimately the pragmatic aspect of language becomes its communicative function. In this case, the impact of the text using emoji is considered to be inseparable from both the content-meaning language means reflecting the author’s intention and the impact aspect with the content-meaning nature of the text with emoji during the act of communication. For this reason, it is considered to be necessary to distinguish the pragmatic aspect during written communication. In order to attract the recipient’s attention, it is necessary to organize communication, express the social relations of the communicants, as well as implement the impact. The main goal of all these indicators is to achieve the desired effect for communication.

The main purpose of using emojis in text is to convey the main nuances conveyed to the reader. Message emojis add additional impact to the meaning of written texts and expand the meaning of it [4, p.5].

L.Olson and C.A. Finegan asked a group of young people: “Why do you use emojis?” The answer is: “To make our messages more interesting, more entertaining. Also, to convey more clearly to our reader, to our friend, the expression on our face when we write the message” [Olson 2008, p.6]. In short, emojis are used to add colloquial expression and meaning to written text. M. Danesi writes: “The use of emojis should be taken quite seriously” [Danesi 2017, p.17]. Meaning does not only include signs. F. de Saussure was one of the first to express his opinion on the nature and essence of signs. He wrote: “Language is a system of signs, and linguistics can be considered as a part of semiotics” [Saussure 1916, p.15]. Emojis, defined as signs, can be expressed in the language of F. de Saussure as following: “Emoji signs are part of social lives”.

Emojis are symbols used in written texts. There has been a growing interest in studying the semantics of symbols in recent years. There is a connection between a symbol and its meaning and connotation. A symbol has a connotation and that connotation has a meaning.

One meaning can express different meanings in different languages, as well as within a language. Emojis are used to convey purpose, mood, and state of mind. They are revelatory signs of our thoughts and behavioral intentions. Nowadays, emojis are considered to be a form of communication that conveys meaningful information in a clear and concise manner.

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